

Kinetic study of iridium(III) catalyzed oxidation of 2-phenyl ethanol and 2-methyl cyclohexanol by cerium(IV) sulphate

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Abstract : Oxidation of 2-phenyl ethanol and 2-methyl cyclohexanol by cerium(IV) sulphate in aqueous sulphuric acid medium is greatly enhanced by iridium(III) chloride. Catalyst combines with the complex formed between cerium(IV) and organic substrate and ultimately gives rise to corresponding aromatic dicarboxylic acids as the product of oxidation. Reactions follows direct proportionality with respect to catalyst concentrations while the first order kinetics shown by the oxidant and organic substrate at their low concentrations become zero order at higher concentrations of both oxidant and organic substrate. Rate decreased with increasing concentrations of H^+ ions. Externally added Ce^{III} and Cl^- ions have negative effects on the reaction rate. Stoichiometry of the reaction was determined and the final oxidation products were identified to be 2-phenyl ethanoic acid and 2-methyl hexane-1,6-dioic acid respectively for 2-phenyl ethanol and 2-methyl cyclohexanol. Complex formation in 2-methyl cyclohexanol is easier compared to that in case of 2-phenyl ethanol.

Keywords : Oxidation, cerium(IV) sulphate, iridium(III) chloride, catalysis.

Introduction

Un-catalyzed oxidation of aromatic compounds by cerium(IV) has been frequently reported from the kinetic and synthetic point of views¹, but proper attention has not been given to these oxidations in the presence of transition metal ions. In the study of aerobic oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols using cyclopentadienyl iridium(III) complex ($[Cp^*IrCl_2]_2$) as the catalyst², it has been suggested that the transition metal maintains its (+3) oxidation state throughout the entire catalytic cycle and iridium hydride is the key intermediate in the catalytic cycle. In alkaline medium iridium(III) chloride shows a sluggish catalytic behaviour^{3,4}. It may be pointed out that we have reported powerful catalytic activity of iridium(III)-cerium(IV) system in acidic medium in the oxidation of aliphatic ketones⁵⁻⁷ from the kinetic point of view. The system is so efficient from the synthetic point of view also that it oxidizes various aromatic organic compounds in excellent yields including cyclohexane and benzene with the highest yields reported so far^{8,9}. To find out the effect of iridium(III) chloride in catalyzing the oxidation of aromatic and cyclic alcohols from kinetic point of view, we have studied the oxidation of 2-phenyl ethanol and 2-

methyl cyclohexanol by cerium(IV) sulphate in aqueous sulphuric acid medium in the presence of iridium(III) chloride.

Results and discussion

First order plots between $\log(a-x)$ versus time for the consumption of cerium(IV) sulphate in the case of 2-phenyl ethanol and 2-methyl cyclohexanol both, show straight lines. However, probably due to the formation of complex, deviations in the later part of the reaction at higher concentrations of the oxidant are pronounced. In the case of oxidant and substrate both at low concentrations, $-dc/dt$ values increase proportionally (Table 1) and the first order rate constants for molar concentration 'k' values show fair constancy, while at higher concentrations increase in $-dc/dt$ values becomes less prominent and 'k' values start decreasing. Further, on plotting $-dc/dt$ versus [oxidant] or [organic substrate] (Fig. 1), straight lines passing through the origin becoming parallel to x-axis at higher concentrations of the oxidant and organic substrate both. All these facts collectively confirm that the rate shows direct proportionality with respect to oxidant and organic substrate both only at their low concen-

Table 1. Effect of variation of [cerium(IV)] and [organic substrate] on the rate at 35 °C

Cerium(IV) variation : (A) [2-phenyl ethanol] = $3.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[IrCl_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$;
 (B) [2-methyl cyclohexanol] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[IrCl_3] = 13.3 \times 10^{-7} M$

Organic substrate variation : [2-phenyl ethanol] : (A) $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[IrCl_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} M$,
 $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$; [2-methyl cyclohexanol] : (B) $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[IrCl_3] = 13.3 \times 10^{-7} M$

$[Ce^{IV}] \times 10^4$ (M)	$k_{obs} = -dc/dt/[Ce^{IV}]$ (min^{-1})		[Org. subs.] $\times 10^3$ (M)	$k^* = k_{obs}/[Org. subs.] \times 10^2$ ($M^{-1} min^{-1}$)	
	(A)	(B)		(A)	(B)
1.43	0.07	-	1.33	1.41	-
1.67	0.08	-	1.43	1.36	-
2.00	0.08	0.13	1.54	1.32	0.52
2.22	0.08	0.13	1.67	-	0.69
2.50	0.08	0.13	1.82	1.24	-
2.86	0.07	0.12	2.00	-	0.70
3.33	0.06	0.10	2.22	1.10	-
4.00	0.06	-	2.50	1.10	-
5.00	0.05	0.07	2.86	0.92	-
6.66	0.04	-	3.33	0.83	0.59
			4.00	0.75	-
			5.00	0.56	-
			6.67	-	0.59
			8.00	-	0.52
			12.0	-	0.47
			16.0	-	0.38
			20.0	-	0.33

Fig. 1. Effect of variation of $[Ce(SO_4)_2]$ (A and B) and [organic substrate] (C and D) on the rate at 35 °C : (A) [2-phenyl ethanol] = $3.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[IrCl_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$; (B) [2-methyl cyclohexanol] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[IrCl_3] = 13.3 \times 10^{-7} M$; (C) $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[IrCl_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$; (D) $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[IrCl_3] = 13.3 \times 10^{-7} M$.

trations and tends to become independent of concentration at higher concentrations of oxidant and organic sub-

strate. Study at still lower concentrations in the case of 2-methyl cyclohexanol could not be performed because the

reaction becomes too slow to be measured properly, yet the trend of line can be obtained clearly. On plotting $-dc/dt$ values versus $[\text{IrCl}_3]$ (Fig. 2), straight lines passing through the origin and on plotting $\log -dc/dt$ and $\log [\text{IrCl}_3]$ slope values of 1.02 and 1.14 were obtained, while the ' k^* ' values remain constant with average deviation of

to $0.20 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M min}^{-1}$ (under the conditions $[\text{IrCl}_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{2-phenyl ethanol}] = 3.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.00 \text{ M}$, $[\text{acetic acid}] = 2.30 \text{ M}$). This observation shows that the concentration of chloride ions has a retarding effect on the reaction velocity.

Fig. 2. Effect of variation of $[\text{IrCl}_3]$ on the rate at 35°C : (A) $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{2-phenyl ethanol}] = 3.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.00 \text{ M}$, $[\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}] = 2.30 \text{ M}$; (B) $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{2-methyl cyclohexanol}] = 5.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.00 \text{ M}$.

22.61 ± 1.35 and 31.85 ± 5.92 , in case of 2-phenylethanol and 2-methyl cyclohexanol respectively indicating that the reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to iridium(III) chloride concentrations in both the cases. Large volumes of potassium chloride required to maintain ionic strength of the medium constant, restricted the study to be conducted at constant ionic strength of the medium. $-dc/dt$ values go on decreasing with increasing concentrations of sulphuric acid and externally added $\text{Ce}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (Table 2 and Fig. 3) in the reaction mixture, indicating that these ions have a retarding effect on the reaction velocity in both the cases. Effect of change in the concentration of chloride ions on the reaction velocity was studied with the help of a standard KCl solution, which shows that increase in $[\text{Cl}^-]$ retards the reaction velocity and the rate values in case of 2-methyl cyclohexanol decrease from 2.35 to 1.68 ($\times 10^{-5} \text{ M min}^{-1}$) (under the conditions $[\text{IrCl}_3] = 1.33 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{2-methyl cyclohexanol}] = 3.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.00 \text{ M}$, while in the case of 2-phenyl ethanol the rate values decreased from 0.32

Reactive species of iridium(III) chloride :

IrCl_3 in hydrochloric acid gives IrCl_6^{3-} species¹⁰. It has also been reported that iridium(III) and iridium(I) ions are the stable species of iridium¹¹. Further, the aquation of $[\text{IrCl}_6^{3-}]$ gives $[\text{IrCl}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^-$, $[\text{IrCl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^-$ and $[\text{IrCl}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ species¹²⁻¹⁴. This equilibrium may be shown by the general eq. (1),

During our study, observation of strong retarding effect of Cl^- ions on the reaction rate indicates that the above equilibrium is shifted more towards the right hand side and IrCl_6^{3-} cannot be considered as the reactive species^{3,4}. Therefore, considering our experimental results, $[\text{IrCl}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^-$ has been considered as the reactive species of iridium(III) chloride in the present study.

Reactive species of cerium(IV) sulphate :

Cerium(IV) forms a number of complexes in sulphuric acid solution. Hardwick and Robertson¹⁵ have reported

Table 2. Effect of variation of [iridium(III)], $[H^+]$ and $[Ce^{III}]$ on the rate at 35 °C

Catalyst variation : $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} M$, (A) [2-phenyl ethanol] = $3.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$; $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$, (B) [2-methyl cyclohexanol] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$; Hydrogen ion variation : $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} M$, (A) [2-phenyl ethanol] = $3.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[IrCl_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$; $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$; (B) [2-methyl cyclohexanol] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[IrCl_3] = 13.3 \times 10^{-7} M$; Cerium(III) variation : $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} M$, (A) [2-phenyl ethanol] = $3.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[IrCl_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$, $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$; $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$, (B) [2-methyl cyclohexanol] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[IrCl_3] = 13.3 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$

$[Ir^{III}]$ $\times 10^6$ (M)	$k^* = k_{obs}/[IrCl_3]$ ($M^{-1} min^{-1}$)		$[Ce^{III}]$ $\times 10^4$ (M)	$-dc/dt \times 10^5$ ($M min^{-1}$)		$[H^+]$ (M)	$-dc/dt \times 10^5$ ($M min^{-1}$)	
	(A)	(B)		(A)	(B)		(A)	(B)
0.14	18.57	-	1.00	-	2.57	0.30	-	3.38
0.18	31.11	-	2.00	1.32	2.10	0.40	6.00	3.23
0.22	30.00	-	2.22	1.12	-	0.50	3.75	-
0.27	33.70	-	2.50	1.00	-	0.60	3.05	3.00
0.30	35.66	-	2.86	0.98	-	0.70	3.00	-
0.34	33.23	-	3.00	-	1.82	0.80	-	2.81
0.38	34.47	-	3.33	0.92	-	1.00	1.65	-
0.46	38.04	-	4.00	0.81	1.52	1.10	1.65	-
0.66	-	23.94	5.00	-	1.95	1.20	1.20	2.55
1.00	-	22.50	6.00	-	1.73	1.30	0.92	2.48
1.54	-	23.11	-	-	-	-	-	-
1.67	-	23.95	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.00	-	21.65	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.67	-	20.52	-	-	-	-	-	-

Fig. 3. Effect of variation of $[H^+]$ (A and B) and $[Ce^{III}]$ (C and D) on the rate at 35 °C; (A) [2-phenyl ethanol] = $3.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[IrCl_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$; (B) [2-methyl cyclohexanol] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[IrCl_3] = 13.3 \times 10^{-7} M$; (C) [2-phenyl ethanol] = $3.25 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 2.86 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[IrCl_3] = 2.67 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[CH_3COOH] = 2.30 M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$; (D) [2-methyl cyclohexanol] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Ce(SO_4)_2] = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[IrCl_3] = 13.3 \times 10^{-7} M$, $[H_2SO_4] = 1.00 M$.

the following equilibrium between various complexes in sulphuric acid solutions of 2 M ionic strength at 25 °C :

Under our experimental conditions, probably total cerium(IV) is mainly present as $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$. Concentration of Ce^{4+} species e.g. in a solution having $[\text{cerium(IV)}] = 0.00125 \text{ M}$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.0 \text{ M}$ may be calculated from (5), which has been derived from eqs. (2) and (3). The value is found to be $1.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ M}$.

$$[\text{Cerium(IV)}]_{\text{Total}} = [\text{Ce}^{4+}] \left(1 + \frac{K_1[\text{HSO}_4^-]}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{K_1K_2[\text{HSO}_4^-]^2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \right) \quad (5)$$

Range of concentration of acid, in which the present study was performed and the steep fall in rate of the reaction with increasing concentration of sulphuric acid indicates that the other species would be present in insignificantly small concentrations and may be considered negligible. Thus, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ has been taken as the reactive species of Ce^{IV} in aqueous sulphuric acid medium, which has been considered by other workers also^{16,17}. On the basis of these results the probable scheme for the oxidation of 2-methyl cyclohexanol may be given as in Scheme 1.

According to Scheme 1, which is also consistent with the stoichiometry, IrCl_6^{3-} gives $\text{IrCl}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})^{2-}$ species in aqueous medium. Organic substrate (e.g. 2-methyl cyclohexanol) firstly combines with cerium(IV) and gives

Scheme 1

the complex C_1 . In the subsequent step complex C_1 disproportionate into a radical, Ce^{III} and H^+ ion. The radical then combines with $IrCl_5(H_2O)^{2-}$ species of catalyst to give complex C_2 , which in the rate determining step gives rise to ketone. In the subsequent fast step H^\bullet , complexed with catalyst, transfers its electron to cerium(IV) to give the original $IrCl_5(H_2O)^{2-}$ species. Generally, in the oxidation of alcohols by cerium(IV) to give carbonyl compounds, both H^\bullet formed by the homolysis of O-H and C-H bonds are taken up by two cerium molecules but it may be possible that attachment of a bulky group with substrate hinders the transfer of second H^\bullet to cerium due to steric hinderance and thus the electron of the hydrogen is transferred to iridium instead of cerium. Now in the subsequent steps 2-methyl cyclohexanone, by taking six cerium(IV) ions and three H_2O molecules, ultimately gives rise to adipic acid. Oxidation of 2-methyl cyclohexanone to adipic acid by cerium(IV) in aqueous sulphuric acid medium has been reported earlier also¹⁸. 1 : 1 complexes between cerium(IV) and alcohols¹⁹ and ketones²⁰ with the elimination of Ce^{III} and H^+ ions are very well documented. Complex of the composition $[ROH.Ce^{IV}]^{4+}$ between Ce^{IV} and alcohols and Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics has also been reported²¹. Similar results have been reported in case of ketones²²⁻²⁷ and cyclic alcohols²⁸ also. Strong retarding effect of Ce^{III} , H^+ and Cl^- ions on the rate in the present study, clearly suggests their elimination before the rate determining step. In the present case formation of complex between Ce^{IV} and the organic substrate is supported by the change of kinetic orders from one to zero and also from the constancy in the calculated rate constant k values in the beginning only when the complex formation is small. Deviations from constancy become pronounced with increasing Ce^{IV} or organic substrate concentrations. Under acidic conditions formation of complex between organic substrate with cerium(IV) is preferred compared to the formation of complex between organic substrate and iridium(III) has already been reported²⁹. Formation of complex between iridium(III) (step I, Scheme 1) and cycloalcohol (step II, Scheme 1) which then combines with cerium(IV) to give the complex C_2 , can also be ruled out on the basis of experimental results because in that condition the final rate law will be inconsistent with a linear plot of 1/rate

versus $1/[Ir^{III}]$ and a linear dependence on cerium(IV) concentrations in the region where there is a linear dependence of the rate on catalyst concentrations.

Derivation of the rate law :

Total concentration of Ir^{III} (in all equations total concentration of iridium(III) is represented as $[Ir^{III}]_T$, and concentration of organic substrate is represented as $[S]$) according to Scheme 1 may be given by eq. (6),

$$[Ir^{III}]_T = [IrCl_6]^{3-} + [IrCl_5(H_2O)]^{2-} + [Complex C_2] \quad (6)$$

Considering equilibrium concentration for steps I to IV and calculating $[IrCl_6^{3-}]$ and $[IrCl_5(H_2O)^{2-}]$ from steps I and IV respectively of the Scheme 1, eq. (6) after rearrangement can be written as eq. (7),

$$[Ir^{III}]_T = \frac{[C_2][Ce^{III}][H^+][Cl^-]}{K_1K_2K_3[Ce^{IV}][S]} + \frac{[C_2][Ce^{III}][H^+]}{K_2K_3[Ce^{IV}][S]} + C_2 \quad (7)$$

Here K_2 includes K'_2 term also.

Now rate of the reaction in terms of decreasing concentrations of Ce^{IV} from step (V) may be given as the product of the rate constant and concentration of the complex C_2 , which is multiplied by a factor of 2 because two molecules of cerium(IV) are required to regenerate the catalyst in its original form. Thus, the final rate law is obtained as given by eq. (8),

$$-d[Ce^{IV}]/dt = \frac{2kK_1K_2K_3[Ce^{IV}][S][Ir^{III}]_T}{[Ce^{III}][H^+]\{[Cl^-] + K_1\} + K_1K_2K_3[Ce^{IV}][S]} \quad (8)$$

Here also K'_2 is included in K_2 .

This equation clearly accounts for first order kinetics with respect to iridium(III) chloride concentrations. Retarding effect of cerium(III), Cl^- and H^+ ions and the nature shown by cerium(IV) and organic substrate concentrations on the reaction velocity are also quite clear. Under the experimental conditions at low concentrations of cerium(IV) and the organic substrate when $[Cl^-] \gg K_1$, the inequality $[Ce^{III}][H^+][Cl^-] \gg K_1K_2K_3[Ce^{IV}][S]$ may be assumed to be valid and the rate law (8) reduces to

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = \frac{2kK_1K_2K_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{S}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (9)$$

Eq. (9) explains the first order kinetics with respect to cerium(IV) and organic substrate at low concentrations. The retarding nature shown by $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]$, $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ on the reaction velocity is also explained. At higher concentrations the reverse inequality $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-] \ll K_1K_2K_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{S}]$ may be considered because the rate values were determined in the beginning of the reaction where the $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]$ concentration will be quite low and at higher oxidant concentrations a small amount of KCl will be required to keep the ionic strength of the medium constant and therefore, $[\text{Cl}^-]$ will also be quite low. With the above inequality rate law (8) gives rise to eq. (10) that accounts for the first order kinetics as shown by iridium(III) chloride up to its manifold variations.

$$-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt = 2k[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (10)$$

The final rate law (8) can also be written in the form as

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]/dt}{[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}} = k' = \frac{2kK_1K_2K_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{S}]}{[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-] + K_1[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+] + kK_2K_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{S}]} \quad (11)$$

Rate law (8) and (11) can be verified by rewriting these eqs. as (12) and (13) respectively.

$$\frac{1}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{2kK_1K_2K_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{S}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}} + \frac{1}{\frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+]}{2kK_2K_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{S}][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}} + \frac{1}{2k[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{2kK_1K_2K_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{\frac{[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+]}{2kK_2K_3[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{S}]} + \frac{1}{2k}} \quad (13)$$

From these equations, graphs can be plotted between $1/\text{rate}$ versus $1/[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$, $1/[\text{S}]$, $1/[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]$, or $[\text{H}^+]$, which should give a straight line with positive intercept on y-axis from where kK_2K_3 values can be calculated. From the slope of

the straight line thus obtained on plotting $1/\text{rate}$ against $1/[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$, $1/[\text{S}]$ or $[\text{H}^+]$, kK_2K_3 values were found to be 10.7, 16.8 and $3.7 (\times 10^7)$ (2-phenyl ethanol) and 3.95, 0.58 and $1.20 (\times 10^7)$ (2-methyl cyclohexanol) respectively. $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]$ will be produced in the reaction mixture only with the progress of the reaction. The rate values were calculated in the beginning of the reaction when a negligibly small fraction of cerium(IV) would have been converted, therefore, for the sake of simplicity, its concentration may logically be ignored while calculating the kK_2K_3 values, which were calculated by the slope of the graph. Thus, while calculating the kK_2K_3 values, concentration of cerium(III) produced in the reaction mixture was neglected. Fair agreement in kK_2K_3 values calculated from three different graphs further supports the proposed mechanism and the final rate law. Arrhenius equation was found to be applicable and from the slopes of the Arrhenius plots and by using Eyring equation energy of activation, entropy of activation and free energy of activation values were calculated and were found to be 21.88 and 15.00 (kcal), -11.06 and -31.59 (e.u.), 25.16 and 24.73 (kcal $\text{g}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$) for 2-phenyl ethanol and 2-methyl cyclohexanol respectively. From the experimental values obtained for energy of activation, it becomes clear that the complex formation in 2-methyl cyclohexanol having a secondary alcoholic group is easier compared to 2-phenyl ethanol in which primary alcoholic group is oxidized. This may be due to selectivity of cerium(IV) sulphate towards secondary alcoholic groups³⁰. Evidences for secondary > primary selectivity have been found in *N*-halogenated reagents, sodium hypochlorite in acetic acid, cerium(IV) catalyzed oxidation of secondary alcohols to ketones and diols to hydroxyketones etc. Negative value of entropy of activation indicates the formation of complex in the reaction as shown in the scheme^{31,32}.

Experimental

Cerium(IV) sulphate (Loba Chemie, $100 \pm 15\%$) was dissolved in 1 : 1 sulphuric acid. Strength of cerium(IV) sulphate was determined by titrating it against the standard ferrous ammonium sulphate (E. Merck, $99 \pm 0.5\%$) solution using ferroin as an internal indicator. Sodium hexachloroiridate(III) (Johnson Matthey & Co.) was dissolved in minimum amount of analytical grade HCl (E. Merck, 37%). Final concentrations of acid and the cata-

lyst were $0.62 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $3.35 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade or chemically pure substances. Considering the insolubility in aqueous medium stock solution of 2-phenyl ethanol (Fluka A.G., 99%) was dissolved in minimum amount of acetic acid (E. Merck, 99%) and was diluted to the desired volume. Concentration of acetic acid was kept constant in all the variations except while studying the effect of acetic acid concentration on the rate. Ferrous ammonium sulphate solution was standardized with potassium dichromate (E. Merck, 99%) using *N*-phenyl anthranilic acid as an internal indicator³³. Progress of the reaction was measured (constant temperature ± 0.1 °C) at different intervals of time by transferring 5.0 ml aliquot of reaction mixture to a fixed amount of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution (in slight excess to cerium(IV) sulphate initially taken) and estimating the residual ferrous ammonium sulphate with a standard cerium(IV) sulphate solution using ferroin as an internal indicator. In all kinetic runs concentration of organic substrate was kept in excess.

Reaction kinetics and stoichiometry :

In the case of oxidant variation the rate values ($-dc/dt$) were calculated at a fixed initial time in the individual plots, while in all other cases values were calculated at a fixed initial concentration. Rate values were obtained from the initial slopes of individual time plots. First order rate constants for molar concentrations '*k*' values were calculated by dividing $-dc/dt$ values with the concentration of oxidant, organic substrate or the catalyst. Orders, with respect to various reactants were confirmed by four different methods. Tables and figures contain initial concentrations of the reactants. Study could not be made at constant ionic strength of the medium due to large volumes of potassium chloride required to keep the ionic strength constant. Stoichiometry of the reaction was calculated after ensuring complete oxidation of organic substrate by the oxidant in different ratios. After completion of the reaction, reaction mixture was extracted with diethyl ether (5 × 25 ml) and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. After re-crystallization with ethanol oxidation products in case of 2-phenyl ethanol and 2-methyl cyclohexanol were identified as 2-phenyl ethanoic acid

and 2-methyl hexane-1,6-dioic acid respectively, by spot test methods³⁴ and chromatographic technique³⁵. IR spectra of the product in case of 2-methyl cyclohexanol showed peaks at 948 (O–H bending out-of-plane), 1274 (C–O stretch), 1420 (O–H bending in-plane), 1692 (C=O stretch) and 3250 to 3420 with a peak at 3375 (broad O–H stretch). However, α -diketones and 2-hydroxycycloketones, which were detected in the oxidation of cyclohexanol by manganese(III) pyrophosphate³⁶ and chromic acid³⁷ and the presence of cycloketones as intermediates could not be detected due to the overlapping of peaks. Stoichiometry of the reaction may be given by eq. (14),

Conclusion

The present study shows that iridium(III) chloride, which is otherwise considered to be a sluggish catalyst in alkaline medium, acts as a very effective catalyst for the oxidation of aliphatic as well as aromatic alcohols in acidic medium when used in conjunction with cerium(IV) sulphate. The present work also demonstrates that it is cerium(IV) that initially forms the complex with organic substrate and not iridium(III) chloride. Retarding effects of chloride, hydrogen and cerium(III) ions on the reaction velocity confirm the removal of these ions before the rate determining slow step. The present iridium(III)-cerium(IV) system is highly useful to oxidize aliphatic and aromatic organic compounds both from the kinetic as well as from the synthetic point of views.

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